

**ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING SOCIAL SERVICES IN
NEIGHBORHOODS(MAHALLAS)**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7379701>

Abstract: In this article, the factors affecting the development of social services in the neighborhoods, the evaluations given by experts to the factors affecting the development of social services in the neighborhoods, the factors influencing the development of social services using the method of expert evaluation are researched.

Key words: social services, social factors, economic factors, ideological factors, moral-psychological factor, man-made factors, expert assessment.

In the assessment of factors affecting the development of social services, researcher A.A. We use the expert evaluation method developed by Bektemirov. According to it, social services are evaluated on a scale of 1 to 5 factors. Experts put a (+) sign on the assessment of the influence of factors. In this case, the evaluation indicators are: 1-2 - factors that have a "weak" influence on the development of social services; 3 - factors that have an "average" impact on the development of social services; 4-5 means that the factors have a "strong" influence on the development of social services.

Based on the method presented above, we evaluate the level of influence of factors on the development of social services in neighborhoods. A total of 110 experts took part in these surveys. The results of the assessment of factors influencing the development of social services are reflected in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Assessments by experts on the factors affecting the development of social services in neighborhoods

A group of factors	Impact on the development of social services indicative factors		Expert assessment (number of experts 110 people)				
	Nº	The name of the factors	1	2	3	4	5
Group I Political factors	1.	Availability of national laws and regulations on social services	0	0	18	37	55
	2.	Changes in the political structure of the state	0	0	0	73	37
	3.	Denial of the obligations of	0	9	9	37	55

		the previous government by the new government					
	4.	Change of tax policy by the state	0	0	18	55	37
Group II Social factors	1.	As a result of the increase in the consumption of social services, the increase in the efficiency of the use of labor force and the employment of the population in socially useful work due to time savings	0	0	55	37	18
	2.	Increase of productivity of social labor at the expense of social services	0	18	25	30	37
	3.	An increase in national income due to the direct and indirect effects of social services	0	0	18	37	55
	4.	An increase in the total volume of consumption of economic resources due to the consumption of social services	0	0	55	55	0
	5.	At the expense of social services, the general education and cultural level of society members will increase, their health will be strengthened, and the standard of living of the population of different social strata, urban and rural population will be brought closer together.	0	18	27	35	30
Group III Economi	1.	Level of satisfaction of population's needs for social	18	14	21	37	20

c factors		services						
	2.	The impact of the social service sector on the reduction of household labor costs and the composition of leisure time	0	73	18	18	0	
	3.	The degree of impact of the social services sector on the quality composition of the labor force and the improvement of the efficiency of social production	0	37	18	55	0	
IV-group Ideological factors	1.	Directionality of ideology (ability to mobilize)	18	37	18	37	0	
	2.	The ability of ideology to change a person's worldview	0	18	18	37	37	
	3.	The unifying (integrating) power of ideology	0	22	15	18	55	
	4.	Socializing (socializing) role of ideology	15	22	27	24	20	
Group V Man-made factors	1.	The importance of social services in the elimination of negative situations as a result of earthquakes, floods, storms, epidemics	0	7	31	45	27	

The data in Table 1 shows that the experts evaluated each factor based on the given criteria. As it can be seen from the information presented in it, the level of influence of each factor on the development of social services was evaluated. If we analyze the evaluation results, there are no experts who rated the factors of the first group as "1", and the number of those who rated the factors of this group as "2" is a total of 9 people.

The number of experts who rated the factors in the group as "3" varies from 9 to 18 according to the factors. The number of those who rated the level of influence of the factors in the group on the development of social services as "4" and "5" is much higher. Its change varied from 37 to 73 people, and all these factors show

that the level of influence on the development of social services in neighborhoods is strong.

They evaluated the impact of the second group of factors on the development of social services in neighborhoods as follows. The number of experts who rated "1" and "2" is a total of 36 people. The number of those who rated "3" varies from 18 to 55. The number of experts who evaluated the factors of the group with grades "4" and "5" varied from 18 to 55. It is clear from this that the factors mainly have an influence at the "moderate" and "strong" level.

The number of experts who evaluated the level of influence of the third group of factors on the development of social services in the neighborhoods as "1" and "2" ranges from 14 to 73, which means that these factors have a "weak" influence.

The results of the evaluation of the factors of the fourth group by experts show that 15 to 37 people rated the factors as having a "weak" effect, 18 to 37 people rated the factors as having a "moderate" effect, and 18 to 55 people rated the factors as having a "strong" effect. It can be seen that the factors of this group have a "strong" effect.

The results of the assessment of man-made factors (the fifth group) show that these factors have a "strong" influence on the development of social factors in neighborhoods (72 of the experts assessed that they have a "strong" influence).

Using the data of Table 1, we summarize expert assessments and determine the factors that have a "weak", "moderate" and "strong" influence on the development of social services. To do this, we summarize the data based on the above evaluation criteria (Table 2).

Table 2

Table for determining the level of influence of factors affecting the development of social services

Group of the factors	Impact on the development of social services indicative factors		Number of experts	Results of expert assessment according to the level of influence of factors		
	Nº	The name of the factors		"Weak"	"Averag"	"Weak"

Group I Political factors	1.	Availability of national laws and regulations on social services	11 0	0	18	92
	2.	Changes in the political structure of the state		0	0	110
	3.	Denial of the obligations of the previous government by the new government		9	9	92
	4.	Change of tax policy by the state		0	18	92
Group II Social factors	1.	As a result of the increase in the consumption of social services, the increase in the efficiency of the use of labor force and the employment of the population in socially useful work due to time savings	11 0	0	55	55
	2.	Increase of productivity of social labor at the expense of social services		18	25	67
	3.	An increase in national income due to the direct and indirect effects of social services		0	18	92
	4.	An increase in the total volume of consumption of economic resources due to the consumption of social services		0	55	55

	5.	At the expense of social services, the general education and cultural level of society members will increase, their health will be strengthened, and the standard of living of the population of different social strata, urban and rural population will be brought closer together.	18	27	65
Group III Economic factors	1.	Level of satisfaction of population's needs for social services	32	21	57
	2.	The impact of the social service sector on the reduction of household labor costs and the composition of leisure time	73	18	19
	3.	The degree of impact of the social services sector on the quality composition of the labor force and the improvement of the efficiency of social production	37	18	55
IV-group Ideological factors	1.	Directionality of ideology (ability to mobilize)	55	18	37
	2.	The ability of ideology to change human worldview	18	18	74
	3.	The unifying (integrating) power of ideology	22	15	73
	4.	Socializing role of ideology	37	29	44

Group V Man-made factors	1.	The importance of social services in eliminating negative situations as a result of earthquakes, floods, storms, epidemics	7	31	72
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It can be seen from the data included in Table 2 that the number of factors affecting the development of social services is 17, and they are divided into 5 groups. The following can be determined from the results of the assessment of the influence of these factors on the development of social services by experts: the level of influence of all factors included in the first group on the development of social services is very high, i.e., 92 out of 110 experts (84%)) assessed it as having a "strong" effect, and 18 (16%) as having a "moderate" effect. 100% of experts assessed the factor related to the change in the political structure of the state as having a "strong" effect. 84% of experts (92 out of 110) assessed its impact on the development of social services as "strong", 9 experts (8%) assessed it as having a "weak" and "moderate" impact. 92 experts (84 %) assessed its impact as "strong" and 18 as "moderate".

According to the results of the evaluation of the impact of the second group of factors (social factors) on the development of social services by experts, as a result of the increase in the consumption of social services, due to time savings, the factor related to the efficiency of the use of labor force in socially useful work and the increase in the employment of the population, respectively, out of 55 (50%) experts " "moderate" and "strong" influence, 18 (16%) of the experts "weak", 25 (23%) "moderate" and 67 (61%) "strong" influence on the factor of social labor productivity increase evaluated. Regarding the direct and indirect impact of social services belonging to this group, 18 (16 %) experts assessed the factor related to the increase of national income as "moderate" and 92 (84 %) as having a "strong" effect. 55 out of 55 (50%) experts have a "moderate" and "strong" effect on the factor related to the increase in size, and the increase in the general educational and cultural level of the members of the society at the expense of social services, the strengthening of health, the livelihood of the population of different social strata, urban and rural population 18 (16 %) of the experts assessed the factor related to the convergence of levels as having a "weak", 27 (25 %) "moderate" and 65 (59 %) "strong" influence on the development of social services.

The third group of factors consists of economic factors, and the results of experts' assessment of the impact of these factors on the development of social services are as follows: the number of experts who assessed the impact of the factor indicating the level of satisfaction of the population's needs for social services as "weak" is 32 (29%). 21 experts (19 %) assessed "moderate" impact, and 57 (52 %) experts assessed "strong" impact. 73 experts evaluated the factor showing the impact of the social services sector on the reduction of labor costs and the content of free time in the household as "weak", "moderate" and "strong", respectively; 18; 19 (66%; 16%; 17%) are experts. 37 (34%) of the experts said that the factor indicating the level of influence on the quality composition of the labor force of the social services sector and the improvement of social production efficiency has a "weak" effect, 18 (16%) have a "moderate" effect, and 55 (50%) have a "strong" effect. " have evaluated its impact.

If we pay attention to the results of experts' assessment of the influence of the fourth group of factors on the development of social services by each factor, the number of experts who assessed the level of influence of the factor of orientation of ideology (ability to mobilize) as "weak" is 55 (50%), and those who assessed it as "moderate" are 18 (16 %), and those who rated it as "strong" are 37 (34%). 18 out of 16 (16%) experts rated the factor of changeability of ideology as "weak" and "moderate", respectively, while 74 (67%) experts rated it as "strong". The opinions of the experts are as follows: 22 (20 %) said "weak", 15 (14 %) "moderate" and 73 (66 %) reported a "strong" effect. 37 (34%) experts assessed the socializing (socializing) role of ideology in this group as having a "weak" effect, 29 (26%) experts as having a "moderate" and 44 (40%) experts as having a "strong" effect.

The last group of factors consists of man-made factors, which indicate the importance of social services in eliminating negative situations resulting from earthquakes, floods, storms, epidemics, and their influence on the development of social services is considered by 7 experts (6%) to have a "weak" effect, 31 experts (28 %) as "moderate" and 72 (65%) as "strong" impact.

Although the assessment of factors by experts is subjective in determining the impact of factors on the development of social services, we will have the opportunity to select factors with a high level of influence.

Conclusions and suggestions

From the results of evaluations of the influence of factors on the development of social services by experts, it is known that most of the 17 factors selected from 5 groups have a great role in the development of social services. If we choose

factors with a "strong" impact, with a level of influence higher than 50%, 11 of the 17 analyzed factors consist of such factors. These factors will be important in determining the development strategies of social services.

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